

Vallon de Nant : Analysis of precipitation data

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Preliminary remark

This working document presents a short overview of the precipitation data recorded in the Vallon de Nant (VdN) catchment at the newly installed meteo station (since summer 2016), with a comparison to available MeteoSwiss and Canton Vaud stations (all outside of the catchment). The real time data can be accessed at <https://www.climaps.com/> (contact Natalie.Ceperley@unil.ch in case you have questions about this).

The glacier station (Figure 1) has been dismantled in October 2019. After one successful winter (2016 / 2017), the station was destroyed twice (winter 2017/2018, winter 2017/2018). Since the access is long and the station thus difficult to maintain, we decided to dismantle it at the end of the SNFS project of B. Schaepli (end September 2020).

Besides the continuous precipitation observations presented hereafter, the meteo stations also record other climatic variables (see www.climaps.com or (Michelon et al., 2017)). In addition, there are high density and high frequency precipitation observations from the two summers 2017 and 2018 (Michelon et al., To be Submitted) with so-called “pluvimates” (Benoît, 2019; Michelon et al., To be Submitted) (**Error! Reference source not found.**).

Figure 1 : Left: Vallon de Nant catchment with location of weather stations and temporary water measurement locations, right: position of the 12 pluvimates deployed during summer 2018 (Michelon et al., To be Submitted)

1 Overview VdN

Figure 2 presents an overview of the precipitation measurements at the three stations Auberge, Chalet, Glacier. Represented are cumulative plots to visualize the long term differences between the stations. Missing data was gap filled by Benoît (2019) with the algorithm developed by Gravey and Mariethoz (2017).

We clearly see that the glacier station records lower amounts of precipitation than the two other stations and that there is a general decrease from the top station (Glacier) down to the lowest station (Auberge). This overall decreasing trend of precipitation amounts towards the Auberge station is also visible in the comparison to the high density observations, whose measurements are all located upstream of the Auberge station (Figure 3). The exact reasons for this decrease still have to be investigated in detail to understand whether this is a *meteorological phenomenon* or an *observational bias*.

An observational bias could in particular arise from:

- i. Precipitation undercatch due to wind (the glacier station is most likely more windy than the others, leading potentially to a higher undercatch) and
- ii. Snow undercatch by the radar-based LUFFT sensors due to wind (a classical problem for all sensors) and due to the lowered radar sensitivity to snowfall, which has a lower dielectric constant than rain. Such a snow undercatch would yield stronger biases at higher elevations receiving more snowfall.

Figure 2 : Cumulative plot of the precipitation at all VdN meteo stations, original data (dashed) and gap-filled data obtained from Benoît (2019)

Figure 3 Comparison of Pluvimates and fixed rain gauges for the summers 2017 and 2018 (bottom).

2 Detection of anomalies: double cumulated plots

A key question to answer for precipitation recordings is how similar two different stations behave over time, to detect e.g. periods when one station shows significant differences compared to stations in the neighborhood. In hydrology, this analysis is generally based on a simple double cumulated plot, i.e. a plot of the cumulated recordings from two stations.

For the three stations in the VdN, we see that the Auberge and the Chalet station show a homogeneous behavior over the observation period (straight line in upper left plot, Figure 4), while there is an anomaly in the plot of the Glacier recordings vs the Chalet (bottom left

Figure 4), which shows up less clearly in the plot of Glacier vs Auberge (top right, Figure 4). This points towards an irregularity in the Glacier recordings, whose origin has to be confirmed.

Figure 4 : Double cumulated plots of the precipitation recordings at the VdN meteo stations

3 Comparison to stations outside VdN catchment

We completed a detailed comparison of the precipitation recordings inside the VdN with neighbouring stations run by MeteoSwiss and the Canton of Vaud (Figure 5 and Figure 6). The analysis clearly shows that all available stations in the Vaudoise Alps record significantly lower precipitation amounts than our stations in the VdN. The analysis also shows that the MeteoSwiss Derborence station has a peculiar behavior (see also double cumulated plot in Figure 6), which suggests that the data from this station should not be used at the moment. Despite its geographical proximity, the MeteoSwiss Sorniot (SOR) station receives much less precipitation (Figure 7). This could be due to the drying up of the air mass above the mountain range, a severe undercatch due to strong wind or a technical problem. This behavior was already pointed out by Brauchli et al., 2018.

The other stations might serve as proxy (e.g. for gap filling) if the amounts are corrected appropriately. An interesting detail to emphasize are the large differences between the two stations in Bex (Figure 5), which might be due to technological differences rather than just local meteorological differences. The same holds of course for the differences observed

between VdN stations and other stations; the VdN stations use radar-based LUFFT sensors versus classical tipping bucket rain gauges for MeteoSwiss and Vaud.

The origin of differences between stations might always partly be due to technological differences, even if the same technology is used at different locations. Depending on the used technology, snowfall undercatch might in fact be extremely different¹. For tipping buckets, undercatch is at least 20% (Magnusson et al., 2014). Unfortunately, the sensors used in VdN (LUFFT) have been excluded from the international snow sensor comparison project SPICE initiated by WMO (e.g. Kochendorfer et al., 2018; Smith et al., 2017). A detailed comparison for VdN will be available in the context of the PhD thesis of A. Michelon (to finalized in 2020).

Figure 5 : Comparison with surrounding raingauges (MeteoSwis, MCH and Vaud, VD)

¹ For details on reference snow measurements, see <https://www.slf.ch/en/about-the-slf/instrumented-field-sites-and-laboratories/flaechen-und-anlagen-fuer-schnee-und-eis/weissfluhjoch-test-site.html>

Figure 6 : Double cumulated plots among some selected stations of Figure 5

Figure 7 : Long term annual mean precipitation measured by the MeteoSwiss network (daily and hourly observations). Note that the data availability period is different for each station. Stations Plans-sur-Bex (daily data) stopped working in 2003. The Gryon and Les Diablerets stations have only daily data. The other stations are part of the automatic SwissMetNet (hourly data). The red crosses indicate snow measurement stations of the SLF (<https://www.slf.ch>). Source: adapted from (Brauchli et al., 2018)

4 Comparison to modelled data

We completed a comparison to the available gridded precipitation data products available from MeteoSwiss (Figure 8). These data sets are obtained either from spatial interpolation of station data (RhiresD, (MeteoSwiss, 2011), daily, resolution 1km x 1km), from data assimilation into a numerical weather prediction model (COSMO1, hourly 1km x 1km) or from station-radar data merging (CombiPrecip, hourly (Sideris et al., 2014)). They have been developed for specific purposes: COSMO1 for real-time forecasting, CombiPrecip for risk management, weather model verification and environmental modelling, RhiresD for hydrological and other modelling purposes.

RhiresD is known to have severe biases at high elevations, due to absence of station data at high elevations and gauge undercatch for snow (Freudiger et al., 2016; Magnusson et al., 2014). The apparent strong elevation gradient for the VdN station locations is certainly an algorithmic artefact (Figure 8). CombiPrecip has great potential for hydrological modeling but VdN is clearly in a radar-shadow area (Foehn et al., 2018), which explains the low values for VdN station locations (Figure 8). The value of COSMO1 data remains to be analyzed in detail but COSMO1 seems to have a wet bias compared to local stations.

Figure 8 : Comparison to precipitation totals over three selected hydrological years. Combi: CombiPrecip, Rhi: RhiresD, C1: Cosmo1. Source : Brauchli et al., 2018.

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